

**CAN BLOCKCHAIN STOP CYBERCRIME IN
THE FINANCIAL INDUSTRY?**

INHALT

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ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Jan Malkus studied theoretical computer science at the Technical University of Braunschweig with the major “corporate management”. To this day, he is preoccupied with technical issues in computer science, especially with regard to advancing technical innovations such as artificial intelligence.

The factors cybercrime and cyber security play an important thematic role, which the author deals with critically in the following and examines the blockchain as a possible solution to related problems.

The internationally successful serial entrepreneur recognizes a great opportunity in new technologies: the optimization and renewal of established, globally used processes, structures and protocols. The global markets are developing rapidly; More and more data about Internet users are stored - therefore it is only logical to find solutions for the introduction of a personal, digital identity that protects personal rights as best as possible and can also make an important contribution to online fraud prevention.

“The new realities of our time are based on facts that we need to bring back to our consciousness. This awareness will open up new possibilities for us and the following generations to reflect on humanity, to correct mistakes and to master new challenges. One of our tasks is to support and position real people as best as possible in a virtual world, to ensure security and to protect personal rights.”

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PREFACE

The internet is a great achievement and enables worldwide communication in a matter of seconds. It is the largest network in the world. In Germany alone:

- 89,8%** are connected to the internet (of all citizens over 14 years of age)
- 165** minutes is the average time Germans spend online per day.
- 66%** of users go online via their smartphone
- 40** million people in Germany communicate via Whatsapp every week

*Source 1

The situation worldwide today is as follows:

- 45%** of all e-mails are SPAM, this corresponds to 14.5 billion SPAM messages per day.
- 73%** of these e-mails are fraudulent or have other negative motives. The damage caused by SPAM amounts to approximately 20 billion Euros per year.
- 80%** of SPAM e-mails (in USA and Europe) are attributed to about 100 organised crime groups.

*Source 2

Due to the ever-increasing crime on the internet, we should think about how to make the internet more secure without at the same time giving up its desired anonymity in several deviations.

Let us all remember how a state revolution in Egypt was made possible solely by internet-based communication platforms, although this would probably have been unthinkable without the protection of the private individual. Today, most people in the world still live in states where there is no fully independent freedom of press and expression. We must create solutions that do not restrict freedom too much, leave privacy untouched and yet protect it from abuse. To say it in advance: no panacea can solve all these complex problems in one step. Nevertheless, it is already possible to improve the internet step by step and make fraud more and more difficult. Above all, the new blockchain technology can make a decisive contribution to making the internet a safer system for all of us in the financial sector.

I. DEFINITION OF CYBERCRIME

Cybercrime includes crimes that are committed with the support of electronic infrastructure. These often occur on the Internet and using techniques that are available there. In a narrower sense, this essentially includes the following crimes:

- Computer fraud and fraud with access authorisations to communication services (identity theft)
- Falsification of data
- Deception in legal transactions involving data processing
- Data alteration
- Computer sabotage
- Spying and interception of data.

In a broader sense, this includes crimes that take place via the internet. These include, among others:

- Phishing in the area of online banking
- Crimes with DDoS attacks (Distributed Denial of Service, for example by causing the overloading of a company network with the result that this company presence is no longer accessible on the Internet)
- Digital blackmail
- Manufacturing and distributing hacker tools for illegal purposes.

These are digital attacks to the damage of others, be it companies or private individuals. The criminals misuse the internet and communication tools such as e-mail services or social networks to commit crimes. Almost all types of these crimes are committed on or via the internet. In doing so, the criminals can very easily disguise both their identity and the “place of action”, which makes prosecution very difficult. Through illegal online shops, narcotics and weapons are offered for sale as well as hacking software, digital identities, stolen credit card data or access to bank accounts. Anyone can order fake identities over the internet for a few thousand euros and make the payment completely anonymous.

Cyber attacks on companies have changed fundamentally. Broad, uncoordinated malware has clearly become less important. Instead, complex, targeted attacks (Advanced Persistent Threat, APT) on companies and their employees, systems, vulnerabilities and data are on the rise. These targeted attacks are predominantly hidden. They mostly use social engineering tactics, spying on individual employees who have accounts and access to confidential data, for example via platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn and Xing. These include administrators or super-users.

If the criminals get into the computers of these employees, they can log into the company network daily, completely unsuspectingly and prepare their crime. Months can pass before they are discovered. During this time the attacker taps into the company's data.

Classic malware is also becoming more specialised, sophisticated and intelligent. For example, there are always new malware that are not identified via signatures and thus bypass firewalls or intrusion detection systems (IDS), and malware that subverts security systems because it has been electronically signed with stolen or forged certificates. It can be assumed that malware, which appears in many variations for different target groups, will continue to increase in the future. This blurs the boundaries between complex targeted attacks and ordinary malware. Criminal programmers are constantly inventing new and complicated tricks to circumvent security hurdles of their attack targets.

Investigative specialists must constantly adapt their work to these changing approaches and try to stay one step ahead of the criminals, which is generally difficult in practice.³

II. CYBERCRIME IN THE FINANCIAL INDUSTRY

A particular focus in the area of finance is data breaches that have led to breaches of protection / theft of personal data through cybercrime. In the years from 2017 to 2018 alone, these increased by 480 per cent. According to a new study by cloud computing company iomart, breaches and the frequency of security breaches continue to increase on a large scale in 2020. Their number increased by 273 per cent in the first quarter alone compared to the same period last year.⁴

This trend is supported by another study published by the security company EfficientIP. Financial companies are attacked more frequently than companies in any other industry. In the conducted survey, 88 per cent of the companies confirmed they had been a victim of a hacker attack in the past year. It can be assumed that almost 100 per cent were attacked and that the missing 12 per cent in the statistics probably did not notice the attack.⁵

The extent of the danger was already shown by statistics from the British financial regulator FCA from 2017: in the three years from 2014 to 2016 alone, the number of attacks reported to the authority grew by 1,700 per cent. No wonder that despite minus interest rates, rising credit risks and growing geopolitical tensions, banks worry about nothing as much as cyber risks. At least that is the result of a new study by the consultancy EY. Through interviews of risk managers of major global banks, EY found that 67 per cent of them fear the theft of customer data, and 53 per cent see the danger of no longer being accessible and able to act after an attack. Moreover, the vast majority of banks - 77 per cent, see the need to hire experts to help prevent possible cyberattacks. Most companies are upgrading their technology to prepare for increasingly sophisticated attacks.

In an increasingly networked and digitalised economy, cyber risks are becoming an ever greater and potentially existential threat. Banks, in particular, are vulnerable due to the complex, partially fragmented IT infrastructure of many institutions, which is built on numerous legacy systems.⁶

The potential damage from cyberattacks can be immense, as shown by a stress test by Singapore's financial regulator in 2019. According to the financial regulator, a serious hacking attack could cost even the most tech-savvy banks up to 20-35 per cent of their quarterly profits, and banks

that have not taken adequate precautions could lose up to 65 per cent of profits. An EY study published last year shows that not even one in two of the banks surveyed is fully or largely armed when it comes to cyber risks. A slight majority of 53 per cent stated that their own institution is only slightly or moderately protected in dealing with such challenges, and 13 per cent of the large banks surveyed even believe that they are still at the beginning of this topic, although attacks are becoming increasingly professional and come from various directions.

Recently, since a spectacular attack in Bangladesh in 2016, the topic of cyber security has been at the top of the agenda for central banks and financial supervisors. The fraudsters were able to extract almost one billion US dollars from the Federal Reserve Bank of New York by tricking a payment system (SWIFT) that had previously been considered very secure. Although they have recovered most of the money, about 80 million USD remained untraced. In Germany, too, there have already been one or two spectacular bank robberies from the Internet. In 2019, cyber criminals from Brazil looted a total of 1.5 million euros from around 2,000 German customers.

The most successful cyber attacks are initiated from „inside“. Attackers are taking more and more time to explore a bank's systems. After they have overcome a financial institution's security measures and infiltrated the IT, they often operate in secret for weeks or even months to scout out behavioural patterns before launching an attack. Hackers have also changed the timing of their attacks. In the past, cybercriminals preferred to make fraudulent payments outside business hours to avoid detection. Now, Swift has identified an exact opposite trend: perpetrators launch their operations during normal business hours to mix their data transactions with legitimate traffic.⁷

III. CYBERCRIME IN THE CORONA CRISIS

Criminal activities often increase in times of crisis. This can be observed especially in the COVID-19 pandemic in connection with cybercrime. The international organisation of criminal police, INTERPOL, has reported on this.⁷ INTERPOL found a significant shift from targeting individuals and small businesses to affecting large corporations, governments and critical infrastructures. As organisations and businesses rapidly deploy remote systems and networks to support employees working from home, criminals are also taking advantage of the increased security vulnerabilities to steal data, steal funds and cause disruption. We can assume that cyber criminals have snuck onto numerous employees' computers during this

time, but haven't even launched the attack yet, as it becomes more effective and extensive when the employee is back working directly on the network at headquarters. In the first four months of 2020, increased attacks on company networks were detected by an INTERPOL partner. Cybercriminals are developing and increasing their attacks at an alarming rate, exploiting the fear and insecurity caused by the unstable social and economic situation due to COVID-19. People's increasing online dependency creates new opportunities for cyber criminals, as many companies and individuals are mostly unable to ensure that their cyber defences are up to date.

Key findings from INTERPOL's assessment of the cybercrime landscape in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic include:

1.) Online fraud and phishing

Threat actors have revised their usual online fraud and phishing schemes. By deploying COVID-19-related phishing emails, often impersonating government and health agencies, cybercriminals lure victims into providing their personal information and downloading malicious content. Around two-thirds of member countries responding to the Global Cybercrime Survey said they have had COVID-19 phishing and online fraud issues on their agenda since the outbreak.

2.) Disruptive malware (ransomware und DDoS)

Cybercriminals are increasingly using disruptive malware against critical infrastructure due to its potential for high impact and financial benefit. In April 2020, there was an increase in ransomware attacks by multiple threat groups. These attacks were very well prepared and each exploited vulnerabilities in IT security systems. How well informed these criminals were is evidenced by the fact that the majority of attackers were able to estimate quite accurately the amount of ransom they could demand from target organisations.

3.) Data harvesting malware

The deployment of data harvesting malware such as RAS Trojans, info stealers, spyware and banking Trojans by cybercriminals is increasing. Using COVID-19-related information, threat actors infiltrate systems to compromise networks, steal data, divert money and create unauthorised botnets. Botnets are networks of computers that can perform activities together, so the victim's network can be used for processes that the owner does not know about.

4.) Malicious domains

Given the increased demand for medical care and information on COVID-19, the number of cybercriminals using domain names with keywords such as "coronavirus" or "COVID". These fraudulent websites support a variety of malicious activities, including C2 servers, malware delivery and phishing. From February to March 2020, malicious registrations (including malware and phishing) increased by 569 per cent and high-risk registrations increased by 788 per cent, detected by a private sector partner and reported to INTERPOL.

5.) Misinformation

An increasing amount of misinformation and fake news is spreading rapidly among the public. Unverified information, poorly understood threats and conspiracy theories have contributed to fears in communities and, in some cases, made it easier to carry out cyberattacks. Nearly 30 per cent of countries responding to the global cybercrime survey confirmed the spread of false information related to COVID-19. In one month, one country reported 290 postings, the majority of which contained hidden malware. There are also reports of misinformation related to the illegal trade of fraudulent medical goods.

A further increase in cybercrime is likely to happen. In particular, the security vulnerabilities associated with working from home can open multiple vectors for criminals for cyber attacks. They will continue to expand their activities, developing more advanced and precise approaches.

Threat actors will likely continue to spread online scams and phishing campaigns related to coronavirus to increase public concern about the pandemic.

Once COVID-19 vaccines are available in large quantities, we can assume that many employees will return to headquarters. Then we will see increased cyber attacks from "inside" again, since the "enemy" has already penetrated the system and is just waiting for direct access to the central computer.

IV. SOLUTION BLOCKCHAIN. HOW IT WORKS.

The threat of cyber crime has been real for a long time. It is currently growing daily and represents an ever-increasing danger. Cybercrime is the fastest growing crime in the world.

Criminals are increasingly moving online because that is where the money is. When looking for ways to effectively combat and contain this threat, it comes down to securing against unauthorised access, as well as securing databases and data information systems against attack by cybercriminals. Blockchain technology can play a key role in this scenario.

The cryptography-based technology offers solutions with unprecedented security and reliability, which already found its first peak in the manifestation of cryptocurrencies.

Bitcoin is based on the blockchain concept and so has its generally recognised security as the first real digital currency. Apart from its use for the cryptocurrency Bitcoin, there are many other possible applications for blockchain technology. A blockchain is a decentralised distributed register that is used, for example, to securely process digital currency transactions. The blockchain is a distributed database where each user/ participant has a complete encrypted copy of all transactions ever made. New transactions only become valid in the blockchain when all, or at least the majority of all, network nodes in the respective blockchain network have verified and confirmed them. Each partial database therefore presents a complete blockchain ledger, and is a continuously growing stack of all transactions that have been executed in the past. Each transaction is recorded in tamper-proof data structure blocks. The completed blocks are added in linear and chronological order. Each block contains a timestamp and an information link pointing to a previous block.⁸

The blockchain is not only considered to be fraud resistant, it also has the highest standards of transparency and all processes can be fully traced even after years.

V. HOW BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY CAN PREVENT CYBERCRIME.

Why blockchain can be a solution to combat cybercrime is shown by its four core properties, which ensure maximum security:

1. Access

Companies repeatedly ask the public and customers to ensure to change passwords, if they were compromised and create strong and unique passwords. However, not everyone does so. According to a research by a password management company LastPass, 59 per cent of people mostly or always use the same password for their accounts, which is often an easily guessed combination, allowing hackers to easily gain access to accounts and internal systems. Blockchain makes it more difficult for unauthorised persons to access confidential data, as explained further.¹⁵

2. Encryption

Blockchain uses a cryptographic procedure, a so-called Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA) with a key length of 256 bits, which is almost impossible to crack. In addition, the digital identity that guardians of the blockchain create for the respective participant is validated by consensus. In practice, this means that the identity must first be validated by a certain number of independent guardians of the blockchain before a participant is granted access. Each blockchain has a number of guardians that maintain the integrity of the entire network. These guardians are by definition independent of each other and distributed in a decentralised manner. An attack on the blockchain can only be successful if more than 50% of these guardians have been overwhelmed and manipulated at the same time, or if they were not independently established in the first place, contrary to the definition.

3. Process security

The manipulation or falsification of transactions or information is virtually impossible on the blockchain. For example, banks, which are obliged by consumer protection laws to take back unauthorised transactions, thus gain with increasing the resources required for security.

4. Integrity

Every transaction is completely visible. It is not possible to forge a transaction or to reject it after it has been executed.¹⁰

Regardless of the advantages of a blockchain, the challenges of implementing a secure blockchain are very complex. The international consultancy Deloitte has asked executives to comment on this. In the Global Blockchain Survey 2019, the evaluation showed that despite the challenges, they have a higher level of confidence in the cybersecurity of blockchain solutions than in any previous cybersecurity of conventional IT.¹¹

However, the blockchain must be designed securely (e.g. the guardians must be independent of each other). It is also possible to adapt existing blockchain solutions to new challenges. If the update of the blockchain software in question does not affect its compatibility with the previous version, this is known as a soft fork. An example of a soft fork was provided by the Bitcoin blockchain with the SegWit update (Segregated Witness). In a soft fork, all network nodes can continue to enter their transactions into the same blockchain and vote with each other on the consensus. If the software update in question removes compatibility with older versions of the blockchain software, this is referred to as a hard fork. This type of update typically interferes with the consensus procedure and/or changes the structure of the data blocks so that the old version of the software cannot deal with the changes. With the first new data block, a new blockchain is irreversibly created. Once all network participants have imported the update of such a hard fork, the old blockchain merges into the new blockchain and thus ceases to exist itself. Thus, only the new blockchain continues to exist. A good example of a hard fork of this kind were the two Ethereum updates Constantinople and St. Petersburg from 2019.

Blockchain technology will continuously evolve. Developers will learn from attacks, manipulation attempts, or other incidents. We must not forget that it is a relatively young technology and experience with very large amounts of data or systems on the blockchain is limited for now. On the other hand, cryptography-based technologies offer a new security standard that has pushed fraudsters to their limits and is therefore now considered completely forgery-proof.

VI. HOW FINANCIAL SERVICE PROVIDERS CAN USE BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY TO COMBAT ILLEGAL ACTIVITIES ONLINE.

Between 2018 and 2025, the global volume of data is expected to grow from 33 to 175 zettabytes (one zettabyte is 1 billion terabytes), according to a 2019 IDC study, a multiplication by a factor of 5.3 - the average annual growth rate globally would be 27.2 per cent. As the volume grows, the dependence on data also deepens. The systems currently still used to store and manage data are no longer sufficient for these amounts. A new approach is urgently needed. This growing mass of data is one reason why more and more cybercriminals often go unpunished. For example, only 1 per cent of the proceeds of this type of crime in the EU are seized by the authorities. Conversely, this means that 99% of the proceeds on cybercrime have been collected with impunity. Nowhere can you cover your tracks as well as on the internet. Only 5% of all compliance requests regarding relevant transactions can be traced in reality.¹¹

The financial industry is disproportionately affected, as this is where the attack is most likely to pay off. The following graph shows the increase in cashless payment transactions worldwide in the years from 2013 to 2022.

Source 12

With more than 1,000 billion transactions, it is obvious that most of them have to run fully automatically. The systems themselves are not the problem, but all interfaces to the transaction systems are gateways for crime. New verification options must be created that more reliably identify intruders and protect genuine users.

One example of how financial products and blockchain can work together is Decentralised Finance (DeFi). It is the generic term for classic financial products that are processed via a decentralised platform - for example a blockchain. In the classic financial world, a bank, stock exchange or insurance company is usually an intermediary that acts as a central point of contact and control for all transactions and services that take place. In DeFi applications, this task is taken over by the network of participants, which follows the specifications in the protocol. It is a blockchain protocol that enables decentralised organisation through so-called smart contracts. These are digital contracts that are embedded in programme codes and can thus replace human or manual transactions. This leads to a high level of privacy protection, as no personal data is processed by third parties, while at the same time there is a high level of transparency due to publicly viewable transactions. Thus, cybercrime is made more difficult.¹³

VII. CONCLUSION

Every cyber attack, which costs financial institutions in particular millions of euros every year, highlights the need for new and innovative solutions. Regardless of which cybercrime solutions are developed to protect financial services in the future, blockchain technology can be a crucial enabling technology here. As more and more institutions adopt distributed ledger technology (DLT), blockchain is becoming the de facto solution for keeping financial data secure. It is already possible to secure a database at a completely different level and virtually eliminate data theft. This is a fundamental step to improve security on the network.

The challenges of each implementation of a new and secure blockchain are individual and indeed very complex. The classic protection goals of IT security, namely integrity, authenticity, availability and confidentiality, have so far fallen by the wayside in many blockchain implementations due to lack of knowledge or unwillingness. Due to the lack of standards and regulatory guidelines, it is up to the individual companies to ensure the DSGVO compliance of their blockchain solutions in order to get operational risks of digitalisation under control at an early stage, especially in their own interest.

Even though the blockchain has its origins in the development of Bitcoin, the technology offers many more possible applications. These can also be used to improve security. For example, in terms of data storage, the blockchain offers significant advantages over established practices because data is not stored in "a single silo" as in many legacy systems. Any conventional encrypted database can be decrypted with today's technology, thus the data can be stolen or manipulated. This is in the nature of the technology: since they are central systems, there is a central key that you have to "find and copy". With this, one has access and can start criminal activities. A blockchain can remedy this. If one has illegally gained access to a server (or a guardian) of the blockchain, one still has no chance to manipulate the blockchain. In addition, the blockchain has the following advantages, because it offers:

1.) More transparency

A blockchain ledger is fundamentally more transparent than other data storage methods, as all actors with access to the ledger see the same data and hold their own copy. A blockchain network therefore acts as a single source of truth for data storage. This also helps regulators and law enforcement agencies to track down illegal activities.

2.) Data integrity

The data stored in a distributed ledger is accessible in real time so that systems can be monitored more proactively for fraudulent activity. Since there is only a single view of a distributed ledger, any changes to the stored data are visible to and verified by each system node. Once stored in the blockchain, the data is immutable forever. This has decisive advantages, as not even several legitimate employees of a company can change the data together. The historical data is thus absolutely forgery-proof.

3.) Security

Data is encrypted and stored across a network of servers rather than a single server. A single server can fail at any time without information being lost or the network being compromised at any time. A cyber-attack can hardly be carried out successfully, because in an attack, over 50 per cent of all servers on the blockchain must be attacked and taken over at the same time.

4.) Authentication and digital identity

A blockchain network could enable and provide a federated digital identity service where authorities, financial institutions and service providers work together to ensure effective customer authentication. This would be an important element in the fight against cybercrime. It is very easy to use a forgery-proof certificate of authenticity on the blockchain to identify things, contracts or people so that the recipient can validate all the details of the transaction without any doubt.

All of these features of a blockchain can help better protect financial service providers from cybercrime.

Protecting against cybercrime is a top priority for financial service providers, especially as the amount of data continues to grow rapidly. Blockchain technology, combined with artificial intelligence (neural networks and machine learning), holds enormous potential for securely storing and sharing data - and thus preventing attacks on it. We are at the beginning of this exciting new technology that can set a new standard in terms of security. However, not every blockchain is secure and perfectly set up. It requires sufficient know-how to fully exploit the opportunities it offers.

Technological progress cannot be stopped; As secure as a well-established blockchain can be today, it can become as vulnerable in the future. Quantum computers are a completely new challenge for all online security systems. With their unimaginable computing power, they could easily decrypt current "insurmountable encryptions" within seconds or minutes at the latest. It can therefore be predicted that quantum computer technology will undermine all current cryptography in the future. But not only attackers are arming: the lines of defence can also be improved. So you should start equipping the blockchain with defence mechanisms against future dangers such as quantum computers. There will be constant competition that is constantly redefining itself on the basis of new technologies.

Technology alone will never be enough to effectively combat cybercrime. Human experience and expertise will always be needed to control systems and detect suspicious activity. If the decision-makers of the threatened companies and industries recognise the opportunities that lie in securing data management and exchange, blockchain technology could be part of a long-term solution.¹⁴

At large, it can be said that blockchain fulfils all the prerequisites for putting a stop to cyber criminals in a number of application areas. In the future, technology will not only improve security in banks, but also in numerous other areas.

Responsible for content

In the paper, the masculine spelling is used for better readability. Unless explicitly stated, this applies to all genders. The paper only reflects the author's opinion and point of view. It was created with the greatest possible care. Regardless of this, the author rejects any liability for contained errors or facts and their correlations.

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